

The Meaning of Initiating Non-departmental Law on an International Treaty Perspective

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Abstract

The issuance of the Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 24 of 2000 concerning International Agreements, is the legal basis relating to international agreements, if observed by Law no. 24 of 2000 concerning International Treaties has not been revised for a long time, although over time there have been many developments from an international perspective. Article 17 paragraph 2 of Law no. 24 of 2000 concerning International Treaties states that a copy of the official text of each international agreement is submitted to state institutions and government agencies, both departmental and non-departmental initiators. Whereas in the provisions of Article 17 paragraph 2 of Law no. 24 of 2000 concerning the International Agreement on the phrase "non-department initiating" in this case the legal meaning of the phrase "non-departmental initiator" creates a vague norm (vague norm) which results in legal uncertainty regarding the regulation of the article which does not explain what what is meant by "non-departmental initiator". That it can be called containing the interpretation of a vague norm in this case is strengthened by the absence of a significant explanation and or a clear and directed explanation to explain the meaning of "non-departmental initiator". The meaning of the phrase "non-departmental initiator" can lead to a vague norm (vague norm) which results in legal uncertainty regarding the regulation of Article 17 paragraph 2 of Law no. 24 of 2000 concerning International Treaties.

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1. Introduction

The Law on International Treaties is the implementation of Article 11 of the 1945 Constitution which authorizes the President to make authority to the President to make international agreements with the approval of the House of Representatives. Article 11 paragraph (1) of the 1945 Constitution states that the President with the approval of the House of Representatives declares war, makes peace and treaties with other countries. Article 11 paragraph (2) The President in making other international agreements that cause broad and fundamental consequences for the lives of the people related to the burden of state finances, and/or requires amendments or the formation of laws must be approved by the House of Representatives. Article 11 paragraph (3) Further provisions on international agreements are regulated by law.

An international agreement is an agreement entered into between members of the community of nations and aims to result in certain legal consequences (Mochtar Kusumaatmadja & ETTY R. Agoes, 2010). An international agreement is an agreement between a state and or other subjects of international law which gives rise to certain legal consequences for each party involved.

Whereas an international agreement is a juridical instrument that accommodates the will and consent of the state or other subjects of international law to achieve common goals, the making of which is regulated by international law and creates binding legal consequences for the parties who make it (Nováčková, D., & Vnuková, 2021). Al Banna (2020) stated that a treaty is engagement between states, governed by international law as distinct from municipal law, the form and manner of which is immaterial to the legal consequences of the act. Free translation which means an international agreement in this case is an engagement between countries, governed by international law that is different from city law, the form and manner of which is immaterial to the legal consequences of action.

The importance of an international agreement for a country that will implement or implement bilateral or multilateral diplomatic relations, it is a must for a country to have a legal umbrella or legal basis for a statutory regulation relating to international agreements, as in Indonesia the existence of a law Law No. 24 of 2000 concerning International Treaties.

Whereas the issuance of the Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 24 of 2000 concerning International Agreements which was published in 2000, if it is observed that the Law has not been revised for a long time, although over time there have been many developments from an international perspective. Referring to Article 17 paragraph 2 of Law no. 24 of 2000 concerning International Treaties states that a copy of the official text of each international agreement is submitted to state institutions and government agencies, both departmental and non-departmental initiators.

The provisions of Article 17 paragraph 2 of Law no. 24 of 2000 concerning the International Agreement on the phrase "non-department initiating" in this case the legal meaning of the phrase "non-departmental initiator" creates a vague norm (vague norm) which results in legal uncertainty regarding the regulation of the article which does not explain what is meant by "non-departmental initiator". That it can be called containing the interpretation of a vague norm in this case is strengthened by the absence of a significant explanation and or a clear and directed explanation to explain the meaning of "non-departmental initiator". The meaning of the phrase "non-departmental initiator" can lead to a vague norm (vague norm) which results in legal uncertainty regarding the regulation of Article 17 paragraph 2 of Law no. 24 of 2000 concerning International Treaties. Therefore, there is a need for a revision of the provisions of Article 17 paragraph 2 of Law no. 24 of 2000 concerning International Treaties.

2. Materials and Methods

This study uses a normative juridical legal research type, which is to examine and analyze legal materials and issues based on statutory regulations (Budianto, 2020). This research was conducted to solve legal problems that arise while the results to be achieved are prescriptions about what should be done (Wiens, 2012). In this case, examining the legal meaning of the substance of the provisions of Article 17 paragraph 2 of Law no. 24 of 2000 concerning International Agreements related to the phrase non-departmental initiator.

3. Results and Discussions

Formation of Legislation

The formation of laws and regulations is essentially the formation of legal norms that apply externally and which are general in a broad sense (Lawton, 2012). The formation of laws and regulations includes two main things, namely the activities of forming the content of regulations on the one hand, and activities relating to the fulfillment of the form of regulations, methods of forming regulations, and processes and procedures for the formation of regulations on the other hand (Cf. Michael, 2022).

Authentic, the formation of laws and regulations is the making of laws and regulations which include the stages of planning, drafting, discussing, ratifying or stipulating, and enacting. Based on the understanding of laws and regulations and the formation of laws and regulations, it can be reformulated the operational definition of the formation of laws and regulations, in the following elements: 1. Making written regulations that contain: legal norms, which apply externally, and which are general in a broad sense or binding in general. 2. Formed by state institutions or authorized officials whose stages consist of: planning, preparation, discussion, ratification or determination, and promulgation.

The importance of the formation of laws and regulations in order to create good laws and regulations, as well as in revising a law in this case Law no. 24 of 2000 concerning international agreements, the theory of the formation of laws and regulations is very much needed.

A state based on law is characterized by several elements, including all acts or actions of the government or the state must be based on legal provisions that existed before the act or action was carried out (Kelsen & Trevino, 2017). The rule of law in this case is the existence of a product of laws and regulations as the legal basis in regulating the nation and state. In the context of the issuance of Law no. 24 of 2000 concerning international treaties is the legal basis for international treaties (Gautama & Hornick, 2022).

Pound (2012) stated that law is the most important institution in implementing social control and/or social engineering. Pound also admits that another function of law is as a means to carry out social engineering. He said that the legal system achieves the goal of law and order (Cf. Selznick, 2020).

The law has determined certain patterns of behavior, so everyone should behave according to these predetermined patterns. In line with Kelsen & Trevino (2017), law must contain 3 (three) identity values, namely the principle of legal certainty (*rechtmatigheid*), the principle of legal justice (*gerechtigheid*), and the principle of legal benefit (*zwechtigheid*) (Langford, et al., 2019).

The explanation of the legal theory is related to the substance of the regulation in Article 17 paragraph 2 of Law no. 24 of 2000 concerning International Treaties states that a copy of the official text of each international agreement is submitted to state institutions and government agencies, both departmental and non-departmental initiators.

The provisions of Article 17 paragraph 2 of Law no. 24 of 2000 concerning the International Treaty on the phrase "non-departmental initiator", in this case the legal meaning of the phrase "non-departmental initiator" creates a vague norm (vague norm) which results in legal uncertainty regarding the regulation of the article which does not explain what what is meant by "non-ministerial initiator".

That it can be said that it contains the interpretation of a vague norm in this case is strengthened by the absence of a significant explanation and or a clear and directed explanation to explain the meaning of "non-departmental initiating" in the chapter on the explanation of the law, it is only stated as Sufficiently Clear. . The meaning of the phrase "non-departmental initiator" can lead to a vague norm (vague norm) which results in legal uncertainty regarding the regulation of Article 17 paragraph 2 of Law no. 24 of 2000 concerning International Treaties.

That from this explanation, according to the researcher, it is necessary to revise the phrase "non-departmental initiator" in Article 17 paragraph 2 of Law no. 24 of 2000 concerning the International Treaty. The reason for this research is based on the interpretation method or juridical hermeneutic interpretation, namely a method for interpreting unclear statutory texts, so that the legislation can be applied to certain concrete events (Bleicher, 2017), in this context the need for interpretation or interpretation is needed. to interpret the text of the legislation contained in the regulation of Article 17 paragraph 2, it is better in the Chapter Explanation of Law no. 24 of 2000 concerning International Agreements in Article 17 paragraph 2 explains the meaning of "non-ministering initiator".

Whereas in addition to the need for legal exposition/construction methods, namely methods that explain words or form understanding (law), the legal understanding in question is legal construction (rechts constructie) which are the tools used to compile legal materials which are carried out systematically in the form of a good term (Aletras et al., 2016), the importance of legal construction (rechts constructie) so that the legal meaning of the phrase "non-departmental initiator" has a clear meaning of legal meaning.

4. Conclusion

That the need for a method of interpretation or interpretation of juridical hermeneutics, namely a method for interpreting unclear statutory texts, so that the legislation can be applied to certain concrete events, in this context the need for interpretation or interpretation is needed to interpret the statutory texts listed in the regulation of Article 17 paragraph 2, it is better in the Explanation Chapter of Law no. 24 of 2000 concerning International Agreements in Article 17 paragraph 2 explains the meaning of "non-ministering initiator". Whereas in addition to the need for legal exposition/construction methods, namely methods that explain words or form understanding (law), the legal understanding in question is legal construction (rechts constructie) which are the tools used to compile legal materials which are carried out systematically in good form of the term. The importance of legal construction (rechts constructie) so that the legal meaning of the phrase "non-departmental initiating" has a clear legal meaning.

Recommendations

Law No. 24 of 2000 concerning International Treaties has not been revised for a long time, although over time there have been many developments from an international perspective. The importance of revising Article 17 paragraph 2 of Law no. 24 of 2000 concerning International Agreements, revised based on the theory of the formation of laws and regulations and the method of interpretation or interpretation of juridical hermeneutics, namely the method for interpreting the text of a piece of legislation.

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